

AQUARIUS Communication and Dissemination Plan I (D7.1)

Seascape Belgium

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1. List of referenced acronyms

AQUARIUS	Aqua Research Infrastructure Services for the health and protection of our unique, oceans, seas and freshwater ecosystems
C&D	Communication & Dissemination
CDP	Communication & Dissemination Plan
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DTO	Digital Twin Ocean
ECR	Early Career Researcher
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICES	International Council for the Exploration of the Sea
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
RI	Research Infrastructure
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
SG	Stakeholder Group
SME	Small and Medium Sized Enterprise
SSBE	Seascape Belgium
TG	Target Group
TA	Transnational Access
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WP	Work Package

2. Summary

This document constitutes the “AQUARIUS Communication and Dissemination Plan I” as Deliverable 7.1 and details the approach to and implementation of AQUARIUS communication and dissemination activities.

The plan is designed to maximise the impact of AQUARIUS activities across all Work Packages, in particular, through raising awareness, mobilising engagement and promoting uptake of AQUARIUS results with target stakeholder groups. The approach to this plan considers the objectives (why), target stakeholder groups (who), key messages (what), timing and phases (when), tools and materials (how), main channels (where), together with key performance indicators. It includes a preliminary calendar of activities for the current period (M1-M18), which will be updated regularly.

This plan will be reviewed for efficacy and updated by month 18 as “AQUARIUS Communication and Dissemination Plan II”.

3. Background and context to the AQUARIUS Communication & Dissemination Plan

3.1. The AQUARIUS concept

Research infrastructures are facilities, resources and services used by the research community to conduct research and promote innovation. They facilitate scientific research within national settings, across borders and in global collaborations.

Europe has a rich landscape of research infrastructures that enable marine and freshwater research and innovation. However, there is a critical need for greater integration of these research infrastructures to facilitate a more collaborative and holistic approach to research and innovation that contributes toward achieving healthy and sustainable marine and freshwater ecosystems, in line with the objectives of the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030. Addressing this need is the central aim of AQUARIUS: to integrate research infrastructures, enabling research and innovation that addresses challenges and explores opportunities for the sustainability of marine and freshwater ecosystems. The thematic and geographic scope of AQUARIUS is inspired by the Mission objectives and Lighthouse regions, respectively.

Figure 1. AQUARIUS geographic scope is informed by the Mission Ocean Lighthouse regions

The specific objectives of AQUARIUS are to:

1. Coordinate the enhancement and integration of a diverse range of top-level infrastructure services;
2. Provide efficient, single-point, transnational access to a broad range of integrated research infrastructures;
3. Design, develop, and manage Transnational Access Funding Calls to the research infrastructures;
4. Facilitate efficient and timely access to the distributed research infrastructure portfolio, for selected projects, according to the needs of the selected user communities;
5. Deliver highly effective training and scientific and technical support for users of the research infrastructures;
6. Ensure advanced data management, interoperability, as well as the connection of digital services (e.g., data services) to the European Open Science Cloud;
7. **Maximise the impact of AQUARIUS through dynamic dissemination, exploitation and communication activities, ensuring that the projects using the integrated research infrastructures can support the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters.**

3.2. Maximising impact

Effective dissemination, communication and exploitation activities are a contractual obligation of Horizon Europe funding. They play a crucial role in ensuring that the project delivers long-term impact and a return on the public investment. They raise the visibility of European research and innovation capacity and ensure that project results are widely shared and made accessible, particularly with target users, thus strengthening the European Research Area and creating a legacy for the project.

To maximise the impact of AQUARIUS, Work Package 7 designs, develops, implements and updates the project's Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Strategy including by:

- Designing an impact-driven Communication and Dissemination Plan, for implementation throughout the project (Task 7.1);
- Promoting outreach and engagement of Transnational Access Funding Calls and ensuring broad dissemination of the project and its results (Task 7.2);
- Fostering and activating paths towards exploitation and uptake of results (Task 7.3); and
- Delivering strategic foresight and road-mapping to bridge the science-to-policy gap (Task 7.4), for impact and legacy.

This document details the AQUARIUS '**Communication & Dissemination Plan**' (CDP) (Deliverable 7.1). It includes the stakeholder engagement strategy, identifying the different target groups (who), the objectives of the CDP (why), key messages (what), timing and phases (when), tools and materials (how), and main channels (where). In addition, it details Key Performance Indicators (KPI) that will be used to monitor progress.

This Plan is a living document that will be updated periodically by the WP7 team and re-issued in month 18 of the project.

Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation activities in AQUARIUS can be considered at two levels:

1. *Level one* concerns the activities, results and outputs across the seven AQUARIUS work packages.
2. *Level two* concerns the selected Transnational Access (TA) Projects, their activities and results.

A separate 'Exploitation Plan' will be developed later in the project as a separate document via a dedicated task (Task 7.3), setting out clear pathways towards the exploitation of

AQUARIUS key exploitable results during and beyond the project. Task 7.3 will also work with the Transnational Access Projects to develop dedicated exploitation plans for their key exploitable results.

4. Why: Aim and objectives

The AQUARIUS Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Strategy aims to maximize the impact of the project through well-designed and dynamic dissemination and communication activities. It has four main objectives:

1. To raise awareness of AQUARIUS, its activities and the value of this public investment amongst diverse stakeholders, including wider society;
2. To maximise engagement of target stakeholder groups throughout the project and beyond, by encouraging applications to the TA Calls and provided training opportunities;
3. To maximise dissemination and exploitation of AQUARIUS results and those of the selected projects towards generating long-term impact for the project;
4. To create an AQUARIUS legacy.

These objectives will be achieved by identifying our target stakeholders, developing tailored messages and calls to action and implementing a strategic approach to delivering these messages at the right time and using the appropriate channels. These aspects are detailed further below.

5. Who: Target groups & stakeholder engagement strategy

Five main Target Groups (TGs) have been identified for AQUARIUS communication and dissemination activities. These are further detailed below, explaining why they are important target groups.

TG#1 – Aquatic research scientists and academia and scientific networks and projects: To promote more collaborative and holistic marine and freshwater research contributing to healthy and sustainable ocean and waters by creating connections, building capacity amongst existing and next-generation researchers in the use of (new) integrated transnational access research infrastructure services, implementing FAIR¹ data management and effective use of virtual research environments for (big) data analytics.

TG#2 - Relevant EU and global Research Infrastructures (RIs), long-term EU and global data services and Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO): To explain the rationale behind AQUARIUS, co-design the portfolio of services, share best practices and promote the value of greater coordination and optimisation within the EU Research Infrastructure landscape and beyond. To anticipate exploitation pathways for the new data generated through enhanced transnational access opportunities through FAIR data management.

TG#3 - Industrial communities and SMEs: To promote opportunities for research scientists from industry to collaborate in TA Projects; to disseminate AQUARIUS outputs and results, promote exploitation and innovation; and, to build the Research Infrastructure community of stakeholders beyond the current project network and scope.

¹ Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable

TG#4 - Policy platforms, decision-makers and funding bodies: To promote the work and value of AQUARIUS; to gather long-term support from policy-makers and funders for the sustainability of the research infrastructure services; and, to demonstrate the value of efforts towards further integration of services and future collaboration across European Research Infrastructures in support of EU and international policy goals.

TG#5 - Wider (non-expert) society including citizen science groups: To build awareness of the project with wider society explaining the importance of the European Research Infrastructure landscape and the added value of AQUARIUS for the European tax-payer. To promote the opportunities for citizen science groups to apply to access the services, the adoption of best practices in FAIR data management, the importance of their role in contributing to Europe’s open data landscape and how this contributes to healthier marine and freshwater ecosystems.

Within the above target groups, specific stakeholder groups have been identified via an initial mapping exercise. These are detailed in Table 1 below, together with the relevant objectives, as well as multipliers and networks to reach these stakeholder groups. This stakeholder activity will be further developed throughout the project with input from all partners, including through the clustering activities in Task 1.4. These stakeholders and activities also build on partners’ own networks, including through previous projects and initiatives.

Table 1. Mapping of key stakeholder groups within the five main target groups, together with multiplier channels and specific communication and dissemination (C&D) objectives. Please note the list is not exhaustive.

Target Group	SG #	Stakeholder Group	Multipliers and Networks	C&D objectives
TG#1: Aquatic research scientists and academia, and scientific networks and projects	SG1	Academic researchers working in marine and freshwater domains, including researchers in vulnerable groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Partner Institutes –University marine and environmental institutes –Scientific networks (see SG4) –Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Raising awareness of AQUARIUS and integrated RI catalogue –Mobilising applications to TA Funding Calls –Targeting ECRs to engage in training opportunities
	SG2	Non-academic researchers in marine and freshwater domains, from, for example, public monitoring bodies, environmental management organisations, or research institutes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –National marine and environmental monitoring bodies –Regional Sea Conventions (OSPAR, HELCOM,...) –ICES 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Promoting collaboration and building research capacity –Engagement in relevant AQUARIUS events and workshops (e.g. brokerage events) –Disseminating scientific outputs and KERS
	SG3	Relevant EU Mission Lighthouse projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Prep4Blue –BlueMissionAA –BlueMission BANOS –EcoDaLLi –BlueMissionMed –DOORS –... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Raising awareness of AQUARIUS and integrated RI –Mobilising applications to TA Funding Calls from relevant scientists –Engagement in relevant AQUARIUS events and workshops (e.g. brokerage events)

Target Group	SG #	Stakeholder Group	Multipliers and Networks	C&D objectives
				–Disseminating AQUARIUS outputs and KERs to support implementation activities
	SG4	EU and global scientific networks, organisations and initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –European Marine Board –JPI Oceans –EurOcean –EuroMarine –Ocean Best Practices (OBPS) –UN Ocean Decade –ICES –Ocean Decade Programme: Early Career Ocean Professionals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Raise awareness of AQUARIUS and its integrated RI –Promote TA Funding Calls and ECR opportunities –Disseminating scientific outputs and KERs –Promote engagement in relevant AQUARIUS events and workshops (e.g. brokerage events)
TG#2: Relevant EU and global Research Infrastructures, long-term EU and global data services and Digital Twin of the Ocean	SG5	EU Research Infrastructures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Partners networks (EMSO-ERIC, EMBRC, Danubius-RI, JERICO-RI, EuroFleets+, EUFAR) –LifeWatch ERIC –AQUACOSM –eLTER –ICOS ERIC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Raise awareness of AQUARIUS and integrated RI –Promote engagement in relevant AQUARIUS events and workshops
	SG6	Long-term EU and global data services and observing initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –EMODnet –Copernicus Marine –SeaDataNet –PANGAEA –EuroGOOS –IODE –OBIS –OceanOPS –GOOS –ECO Ocean Data Sharing –UN DCO Ocean Observing –UN DCC Ocean Prediction –NOAA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Implementation of best practices in RI integration –Uptake of new dataflows and data products from AQUARIUS RI –Dissemination and exploitation of AQUARIUS outputs and KERs
	SG7	Digital twin & EOSC community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –EDITO-Infra –EDITO-ModelLab –DITTO –Iliad –Blue-Cloud –TURTLE –DTO-BioFlow 	

Target Group	SG #	Stakeholder Group	Multipliers and Networks	C&D objectives
TG#3: Industrial communities and SMEs	SG8	Industry representative groups, clusters, networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Blue Invest –Blue Skills –European Aquaculture Industry (EATiP) –Ocean Energy Europe –DBAN (Bulgaria, Ukraine, Georgia) –FUGRO –DEME –De Blauwe Cluster 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Raise awareness of AQUARIUS and its integrated RI –Promote TA calls and ECR opportunities to solicit applications –Promote engagement in relevant AQUARIUS events and workshops (e.g. brokerage events) –Dissemination and exploitation of AQUARIUS (and projects) KER
TG#4: Policy platforms, decision-makers and funding bodies	SG9	EU institutions and initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –EC DG MARE –EC DG ENV –EC DG R&I –DG DEFIS –DG CLIMA –DG Regio –JPI Oceans (funding) –EU JRC –EU Mission Ocean and Waters –Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Raise awareness of AQUARIUS and its integrated RI –Promote engagement in relevant AQUARIUS events and workshops –Dissemination and uptake of AQUARIUS policy brief
	SG10	National authorities/government ministries with responsibility for marine/environmental management.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Regional Sea Conventions (i.e. HELCOM, OSPAR, Black Sea Commission, UNEP-MAP) 	
	SG11	International policy and initiatives, and international governance bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –CBD Secretariat –BBNJ Secretariat –IOC UNESCO 	
TG#5: Wider (non-expert) society including citizen science groups	SG12	Citizen science groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –EU4Ocean Coalition –Youth4Ocean 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Raise awareness of AQUARIUS and its societal relevance –Promote TA calls to include citizen science groups within projects –Dissemination of relevant AQUARIUS outputs and materials –Promote engagement with relevant events and workshops (e.g. brokerage event and final event)
	SG13	NGOs in marine and environmental arena	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –SUBMON –WWF –SeasAtRisk –Surfriders –Wetlands International Europe –GreenPeace –Living Rivers Europe –Sea shepherd –... 	
	SG14	Ocean literacy organisations/advocates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Ecsite –Nausicaa –Plastic Pirates EU 	
	SG15	Media organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –EuroNews 	
	SG6	Teachers and trainers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Network of Blue Schools 	

6. What: Key Messages

The following key concepts will be used to structure and articulate the different AQUARIUS communication messages, considering the specific needs and opportunities to which AQUARIUS responds:

Challenges and opportunities

- Europe has a rich landscape of marine and freshwater research infrastructures the integration of which can facilitate more collaborative and interconnected research and innovation to address urgent global challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss, marine pollution and ocean acidification.
- Considering the interconnectedness of our rivers, seas and ocean, there is a critical need for a more integrated and coordinated research infrastructure landscape.
- Europe's research community (comprising scientists from academic, public bodies, industry and citizen science groups) may not be aware of the availability and potential of existing research infrastructures to advance research and innovation. Depending on their region or institutional capacity they may have difficulty accessing them, and/or lack the technical capacity to use them.

AQUARIUS added value

- For the first time AQUARIUS brings together 57 leading European research infrastructure services to facilitate more collaborative and systemic research that will contribute towards achieving healthy and sustainable marine and freshwater ecosystems.
- AQUARIUS will launch two competitive Transnational Access Funding Calls. Through a robust and transparent evaluation process, AQUARIUS will select research and innovation projects that convincingly demonstrate how they will integrate research infrastructures and contribute to one of the goals of the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters in a relevant Mission Lighthouse region.
- Through enabling more holistic research on marine and freshwater ecosystems, AQUARIUS will support the development phase of the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters, the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership, the European Green Deal, and international climate initiatives.
- AQUARIUS will serve the needs of research and innovation activities in the Mission Lighthouse regions: the Atlantic - Arctic, Baltic and North Sea, Danube and Black Sea, and Mediterranean Sea as well as in their major associated rivers (Danube, Elbe, Ebro or Burrishoole catchment).
- AQUARIUS will create a respected and trusted integrated 'Aqua Infrastructure' in Europe, representing the best of European research infrastructure and its international collaborators.

Examples of key messages tailored to specific target groups are outlined in Table 2, below.

Table 2. Examples of key messages tailored to specific target groups

Target Group	Key messages
<p>TG#1: Aquatic research scientists and academia, and scientific networks and projects</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –For the first time AQUARIUS brings together 57 leading European research infrastructure services to facilitate more collaborative and systemic research that will contribute towards achieving healthy and sustainable marine and freshwater ecosystems. –AQUARIUS will launch two Transnational Access Funding Calls seeking proposals from research and innovation projects that can demonstrate how they will integrate multiple AQUARIUS infrastructures and respond to the call challenges. –AQUARIUS will provide free access to the infrastructure for scientists from the selected projects, including the necessary logistical, technical and scientific support. –AQUARIUS will prepare the new generation of marine and aquatic researchers through specific training in using the research infrastructures. –AQUARIUS will provide dedicated training on data management and data stewardship to ensure that researchers implement best practices in open data, and are aware of existing European data infrastructures, services and tools for processing, documenting, and ingesting their newly collected data and data products. –AQUARIUS will launch internship Open Calls for early career marine and freshwater scientists and technicians, including opportunities to participate in marine internships or floating universities. –AQUARIUS use case scenarios and success stories demonstrate a ‘systems thinking’ approach in the use of integrated research infrastructures to advance research and innovation that contributes to healthier and more sustainable marine and freshwater ecosystems.
<p>TG#2: Relevant EU and global Research Infrastructures, long-term EU and global data services and Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – For the first time, AQUARIUS brings together diverse Research Infrastructures in Europe, demonstrating the benefits and highlighting best practices in integrating research infrastructures and contributing to the European Research Area. –Key European data infrastructures, data services and long-term EU and global initiatives, including digital twins, will benefit from the new data flows through enhanced FAIR data management. –AQUARIUS will contribute to strengthen the EU and global marine & freshwater digital knowledge system, including the future EU Digital Twin Ocean to inform policy objectives of the EU Green Deal, the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030”, and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, as well as contributing to the European Partnership “A climate neutral, sustainable and productive Blue Economy”.
<p>TG#3: Industrial communities and SMEs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –For the first time AQUARIUS brings together 57 leading European research infrastructure services to facilitate more collaborative and systemic research and innovation relating to marine and freshwater ecosystems. –AQUARIUS Research Infrastructures are crucial enablers of research and technological innovation. –AQUARIUS will launch two Transnational Access Funding Calls to solicit proposals from research and innovation projects, including scientists from the private sector, that can demonstrate how they will integrate multiple AQUARIUS infrastructures and respond to the call challenges.

Target Group	Key messages
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -AQUARIUS will implement standardised access procedures, to facilitate open EU industrial research and innovation. -AQUARIUS will provide free and open access to new data flows, data products and project results.
TG#4: Policy platforms, decision makers and funding bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -AQUARIUS will enhance and further integrate research and innovation capacities in support of the development and implementation phases of the EU Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030', the European Green Deal, the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership, and international climate initiatives. It will also be an essential component in achieving the European Digital Twin of the Ocean and the UN Decade for Ocean Sciences (2021-2030). -AQUARIUS Transnational Access Funding Calls will focus on key Mission Ocean Lighthouse Regions. -AQUARIUS will focus on challenge-driven and solution-focused research, that will benefit evidence-based marine and freshwater policies, with positive societal, environmental, technological and economic impacts for Europe. -The legacy of AQUARIUS will be consolidated into a strategic vision for the European Marine Research Infrastructures of the future, working in tandem with participants and stakeholders towards ensuring better coordination and optimisation of RIs in the future. -The AQUARIUS strategic vision policy brief will guide policymakers and funders in their efforts towards further integration of services and future collaboration across European RIs.
TG#5: Wider (non-expert) society including citizen science groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Europe has a rich landscape of marine and freshwater Research Infrastructures which are essential for research and innovation that addresses urgent global challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss, marine pollution and ocean acidification -AQUARIUS will launch two Transnational Access Funding Calls to solicit proposals from research and innovation projects, including citizen scientists, that can demonstrate how they will integrate multiple infrastructures and respond to the call challenges. -Citizen science groups are increasingly important as collectors and providers of FAIR environmental data, AQUARIUS adopts best practices in FAIR data management, and provides access to a range of resources and training materials to support open data practices.

7. When: communication and dissemination phases

While communication and promotion of the project will begin at the onset of the project and continue throughout the entire four years, dissemination activities will begin with the publication of the first project results. Three overlapping communication and dissemination phases are planned, each with a distinct purpose and within which there will be dedicated campaigns. These phases and campaigns are explained further below. Campaigns will be updated throughout the project.

7.1. Phase 1 – Awareness & Promotion (M1-M48)

Purpose: To raise awareness and visibility of AQUARIUS with all stakeholder groups.

Communication and dissemination material will be produced to introduce the project and highlight its activities to all five target groups. This phase will run throughout the entire project. Planned campaigns for the first eighteen months are indicated below. Others will

be added as the project progresses. This phase includes highlighting news, activities and outputs, from both AQUARIUS and from the successful Transnational Access Projects, as well as activities in the wider landscape in which AQUARIUS sits.

Planned communication campaigns supporting Phase 1:

- AQUARIUS kicks-off
- Get to know AQUARIUS, its partners, objectives and upcoming activities
- Launch of the AQUARIUS online searchable Research Infrastructure Catalogue
- Pre-launch of first Transnational Access Funding Call
- The role of Research Infrastructures in the European Research Area
- Meet our Research Infrastructure Providers
- Meet our successful Transnational Access Projects (Calls 1 & 2)
- Follow our Transnational Access Projects' campaigns (Calls 1 and 2)
- ...

7.2. Phase 2 – Outreach & Engagement (M7-M48)

Purpose: To promote active engagement with AQUARIUS opportunities.

This phase will target stakeholders with specific 'calls to action' to mobilise their involvement with AQUARIUS activities. A significant focus of this phase will be to solicit applications to the Transnational Access Funding Calls via two dedicated outreach and engagement campaigns (one for each call). As such, the most important target groups for this phase will be research scientists from TG#1 – TG#3, and citizen scientists from TG#5. This phase will also highlight the AQUARIUS training opportunities, particularly those for early-career researchers (ECR), i.e., the calls for marine internships and floating universities. It will also encourage registration to other AQUARIUS events (e.g. brokerage events, targeted meetings with industry, and webinars). While the main thrust of this activity will be from month seven to the close of the second Transnational Access Funding Call, the ECR and training opportunities and other opportunities for engagement (including engagement with the activities of the Transnational Access Projects, where relevant) will run throughout the project.

Planned campaigns supporting Phase 2:

- Register for our brokerage events
- Transnational Access Funding Call 1 (Sep 2024-Feb 2025): Themes, Eligibility and Evaluation criteria, Use cases, Learn to use the call platform, Apply now!
- Transnational Access Funding Call 2 (Jun-Oct 2025): Themes, Eligibility and Evaluation criteria, Use cases, Learn to use the call platform, Apply now!
- Calling all early career researchers and marine technicians:
 - Apply to marine internships
 - Apply to floating universities
- Join our webinar(s) on FAIR data management
- Join our webinar to learn about the Blue Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE)
- Join our technical training webinars
- Visit the Training Hub on the website

7.3. Phase 3 – Uptake (M7-M48)

Purpose: To disseminate project key exploitable results (KER) and outputs (deliverables, factsheets, infographics, training webinars, data flows and products), both from AQUARIUS itself and from the successful Transnational Access Projects as a first step towards their exploitation (this will be further planned in Task 7.3).

Project outputs and results (KERs) will be disseminated to the relevant stakeholder groups who can exploit from TG#1, TG#2, TG#3, TG#4 and TG#5.

Planned campaigns supporting Phase 3:

- AQUARIUS data gaps report is now available
- AQUARIUS call priorities report is now available
- AQUARIUS resources on FAIR data management are now available
- New dataflows are available
- Training webinars are available
- Transnational Access Project results are available
- Launch of the AQUARIUS policy brief
- AQUARIUS legacy

All phases will be supported by planned and targeted content shared via the various channels (described further in Sections eight, nine and ten below) and where relevant implementing the pay-per-view campaign to broaden outreach or target specific audiences.

8. How: Tools and Materials

8.1. Project branding & visual identify

The first step in any project communication and dissemination strategy is to create a strong and recognisable visual identity through common branding on all communication materials, channels, activities and outputs. The brand identity for AQUARIUS is based on the project logo.

8.1.1. The AQUARIUS logo

The AQUARIUS logo was developed and evolved during the project proposal stage in discussion with partners (Figure 2). The agreed logo (Figure 3) conveys the land-river-ocean connection of aquatic ecosystems through an abstract visual. The colours also reflect the different ecosystem components relevant to AQUARIUS, from land (green), river and coastal (shades of blue), and ocean (blue wave). Finally, the dashed lines represent the technological aspect of AQUARIUS.

Figure 2. The development process of the AQUARIUS logo

Figure 3. The AQUARIUS logo

8.1.2. Branding guidelines

A user-friendly branding guideline (Figure 4) was shared with the project consortium, together with a toolkit of branded templates (Word, PowerPoint) to ensure that the integrity of the AQUARIUS brand extends through all visual communications, documents and reports, creating consistency in communications and recognition for AQUARIUS.

Figure 4. AQUARIUS branding guidelines

8.1.3. AQUARIUS tagline

The following tagline was developed at the start of the project for integration in AQUARIUS communication channels and materials.

Integrating Research Infrastructures - Connecting Scientists - Enabling Transnational Access
For healthy and sustainable marine and freshwater ecosystems

8.1.4. Visual background/visualiser

A key visualizer was created as a background for PowerPoint slide decks, and as a virtual background that can be used during webinars and videoconferences in e.g. Zoom, to promote a strong brand identity through various communication activities.

Figure 5. AQUARIUS visualiser

In keeping with the contractual requirements of Horizon Europe funding, the following funding acknowledgment, disclaimer statement, and EU emblem (Figure 6) are a staple of all branded communication material and appear in the footer of templates and materials (flyers, posters, etc).

Figure 6. Acknowledgement of funding statement and disclaimer

8.2. Communication and dissemination materials

The following materials have been developed or are planned for production and will be available to support the implementation of communication and dissemination activities.

Branded materials

To promote AQUARIUS at events and workshops, some branded materials (Figure 7), carrying the AQUARIUS logo, QR code and/or website URL have been designed and ordered. Currently, these include stickers for laptops, AQUARIUS pins, USB-A to Micro-B and Type-C USB lanyards, bamboo pens, and chocolates.

In choosing these materials, consideration is given to the sustainability of the materials used, their potential usefulness to receivers and effectiveness as promotional materials (QR codes and URL where possible).

To mark the online kick-off event a “goodie bag” was sent to each partner to promote a sense of identity and raise the visibility of AQUARIUS within their own networks.

Figure 7. AQUARIUS branded materials

Project Powerpoint slide deck

A general project presentation has been produced in PowerPoint for consortium partners to disseminate AQUARIUS information at conferences, events and meetings (Figure 8). It provides a comprehensive overview of the project, the consortium, objectives, work plan, activities and opportunities. It can be used as a stand-alone presentation to introduce AQUARIUS at events and meetings, for dissemination material, and individual slides can be incorporated into other presentations needed for specific purposes and audiences. Key slides are updated and added as the project progresses.

Figure 8. AQUARIUS introductory slide-deck.

Brochure

A general AQUARIUS project brochure has been produced to introduce AQUARIUS to all target groups (Figure 9). It contains summary information on the project's key facts (funding, consortium, timeline), and focuses on the main aspects of AQUARIUS, the integration of research infrastructures and the Transnational Access Funding Calls. The brochure will be available in both digital and print versions (in a fold-out format) and include the website QR code.

FRONT

OPEN

BACK

FULL OPEN

Figure 9 AQUARIUS brochure

Poster

A general poster has been produced to support activities in the early phases of the project, to explain the AQUARIUS concept and the opportunities it offers, with an emphasis on the Transnational Access Funding Calls (Figure 11). The poster is scalable to fit various requirements, ensuring its suitability for conferences and meetings. Upon request from partners, more posters may be produced.

Integrating Research Infrastructures - Connecting Scientists - Enabling Transnational Access
For healthy and sustainable marine and freshwater ecosystems

Four years (Mar 2024 - Feb 2028) | 45 Partners (18 national) | €14.5 Million Horizon Europe Funding

Research Infrastructure Catalogue
For the first time AQUARIUS will bring together a portfolio of 57 diverse research infrastructures, ranging from satellites to research vessels, and from drones to laboratory research facilities (+ 10 Data Centers & Virtual Labs), in an online searchable catalogue.

Free on-site, remote and virtual access to these research infrastructures will be provided through two transnational access funding calls.

Participating RIs: [Logos of participating research infrastructures]

Infrastructure catalogue offered in AQUARIUS:
1 Research Vessels, 2 Mobile Marine Observation Platforms (MOPs), 3 Satellites, 4 Environmental Research Facilities, 5 Data Centers & Virtual Labs, 6 Drones, 7 Ocean Observatories, 8 Marine Robotics, 9 Data Centers & Virtual Labs, 10 Data Centers & Virtual Labs

Transnational Access Funding Calls
Transnational access (TA) to AQUARIUS infrastructure will be provided via a competitive call process. Researchers across the marine and freshwater domains are invited to submit project proposals making use of multiple research infrastructure services and demonstrating how their project will contribute to at least one of the EU Mission 'Ocean and Waters' objectives in one of the EU Mission Ocean Lighthouse Regions.

TA Call 1 - Open: 11 November 2024 - 20 January 2025
TA Call 2 - Open: 2 September 2025 - 28 October 2025

Technical Training
AQUARIUS will offer a diversity of training opportunities to infrastructure users, early career scientists and to the wider marine and freshwater research community.

Open Science, Open Data
AQUARIUS will implement best practices in open science and open data, making all data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable & Reusable), data, data products and knowledge become part of the leading European data infrastructures for long-term stewardship and wide access, and maximising the return on investment from AQUARIUS and the successful transnational access projects.

Maximising Impact
AQUARIUS will maximize impact through effective and targeted dissemination, exploitation, and communication of project research and innovation activities and results.

FAIR DATA

IMPACT

Funded by the European Union

hello@aquarius-r1.eu | @aquarius-r1 | @AquariusR1 | @Aquarius-R1 | @aquarius_r1

Figure 11. AQUARIUS poster

Pull-up banners

Two pull-up banners have been produced for AQUARIUS events (Figure 12), specifically the first brokerage events. Others will be created as the project progresses.

Figure 12. AQUARIUS pull-up banner

Videos

Two short (two to five-minute) videos will be produced during the project. The first promotional project video will be produced by month 12, and feature short interviews with key project partners, images of the research infrastructures and animations of AQUARIUS visuals and infographics. A second, legacy video will be produced towards the end of the project. Video shorts will be produced to promote events and project highlights on social media throughout the lifecycle of the project, in particular in advance of each Transnational Access Funding Call as “call to action” teasers for social media. Edits from interviews with consortium members and recipients of funding calls may be considered to promote the impact of success stories across social media, YouTube and suitable events offering video walls.

Figure 13. A spontaneous teaser video produced in ZOOM during the AQUARIUS Kick-Off meeting (April 2024) to convey the connectivity that AQUARIUS will provide between researchers and RIs

9. Where: Channels

9.1. Project website

The AQUARIUS website at AQUARIUS-RI.eu is much more than a project website. In addition to being the primary source of all information on AQUARIUS and a key media channel for promoting the opportunities offered by AQUARIUS, and supporting the uptake of results (from both AQUARIUS and the successful Transnational Access Projects), it has the following specific purposes:

1. Host the interactive AQUARIUS Research Infrastructure Catalogue, containing images, maps and detailed factsheets for each of the research infrastructures (provided by WP4);
2. Source of information on Transnational Access Funding Calls and link to the Transnational Access Platform (TAP) (provided by WP2 and 4)
 - Information on Transnational Access Funding Calls, including challenge areas, eligibility criteria, evaluation process, scientific expert panel, and example use cases.
 - Gateway to the Transnational Access Platform
3. AQUARIUS Training Hub – Technical Material Repository (provided by WP5)
 - How to use the Transnational Access Platform
 - Research infrastructure technical training materials/links
 - Opportunities for early career scientists and technicians (floating universities and marine internships)
 - Data management and use of Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment
 - Links to resources related to the ‘healthy waters and ocean’
 - AQUARIUS newsletter and subscription form
4. Link to AQUARIUS Data Dashboard and relevant resources, including data management plans (provided by WP6)
5. ‘Meet the AQUARIUS Transnational Access projects’ page
6. Central source of all AQUARIUS outputs and dissemination materials

The website also includes a form where visitors can sign up to the AQUARIUS newsletter, as well as a ‘contact us’ email and direct links to AQUARIUS social media.

The first version of the website was developed for the online AQUARIUS kick-off meeting (April 2024) to provide an official information channel for interested stakeholders alerted by social media posts. It launched with general information on the project, contact details, and call-to-action buttons to encourage newsletter subscriptions.

A substantial upgrade to the website will be delivered as part of Deliverable D7.3 (M6) to meet the purposes listed above, where the relevant information is available. Post this official launch (to coincide with the launch of the Research Infrastructure Catalogue), the website will evolve to respond to emerging requirements and new outputs. It will be continuously maintained and updated to provide the ongoing storytelling of project activities.

Traffic to the website will be primarily driven through social media and banners placed strategically on the websites of partners to leverage the opportunity for promotion when the Transnational Access Funding Calls open. In addition, effective meta tags for Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) have been implemented on each page.

Google Analytics is being used to monitor site traffic. Statistics will be assessed regularly to ensure the numbers support targeted Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). If not, action will be taken to increase the visibility via social media and/or other relevant channels.

Figure 14. Screenshots from the AQUARIUS website

9.2. Social media

Social media will be a vital channel to support communication through each phase of the Communication and Dissemination Plan. Independent social media accounts have been established for AQUARIUS under the “project” category on X, LinkedIn, Facebook, and Instagram. LinkedIn will be the primary channel in the first six months. A short Slido poll, launched during the kick-off meeting, indicated that partners considered LinkedIn as the most relevant channel to reach AQUARIUS’ targeted stakeholders. Posts will also be published on X, and engagement level will be monitored. Facebook and Instagram will be activated to reach the wider societal audience. A YouTube channel will be created for AQUARIUS webinars and video material.

The social media strategy involves attracting interest from stakeholders via visually compelling graphics and engaging content describing project information, activities, especially focusing on outreach at events. Social media will be an important channel for advertising the Transnational Access Funding Calls; vigorous campaigns will be developed

and implemented to facilitate the promotion of the two calls (supported also by the Pay Per Click campaign to maximise the reach to target audiences).

While the project name should always be written in full caps, the common use of the word 'Aquarius' and limitations on social media handles required the development of different handles (as outlined below).

Table 3. AQUARIUS social media channels

Channel	Link
Twitter	https://x.com/AquariusRii
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/aquarius-ri/
Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/aquarius_ri
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/people/Aquarius-Ri

Social media approach

AQUARIUS will adopt best practices in social media to promote engagement, according to the following guiding principles:

- Consider the purpose of the post: Who is it aimed at and what do we want to achieve. Is the tone and message appropriate?
- Be informative and add value: Teaser posts to create awareness and trigger interest in upcoming activities/opportunities. Posts to highlight new information. 'Calls to action' to engage in AQUARIUS activities or events.
- Drive traffic to the AQUARIUS website: Link to relevant material on the AQUARIUS website, e.g. Research Infrastructure Catalogue, Transnational Access Funding Calls platform, application forms for training activities, project results and outputs.
- Be engaging: Lead with an interesting, relevant question or statement that relates to the content of the post.
- Use compelling visuals: Photography, animated visuals, infographics, eye-catching posters.
- Optimal timing of posts: Leverage relevant dates in the calendar or current trends.
- Tag handles with large and relevant communities.
- Use hashtags: Customised for nature of content and specific stakeholders.
- Use emojis that are easy to understand and relevant for posts.
- When retweeting content, always retweet with a quote and making the relevance to AQUARIUS clear.
- Consistency: Maintaining engaging content on a regular basis.
- Establish a strategy for comments: Reply in a positive and timely manner. Block spam and refer questions to subject matter experts as appropriate.

In the first six months of the project, AQUARIUS social media focused on introducing the project and rolling out teaser posts to trigger interest in the upcoming launch of the Research Infrastructure Catalogue and Transnational Access Funding Calls. The purpose was to build awareness, test hashtags, gain followers and identify early influencers.

From Month 7, social media posts will focus on the launch of the Research Infrastructure Catalogue, and the launch of TA Call 1, driving traffic to the relevant webpages. There has been and will continue to be a minimum of one post per week, with the aim to build the network and promote engagement.

To ensure consistency of AQUARIUS messaging and style, social media toolkits have been developed and will be rolled out to partners for the specific campaigns.

Content territories of the AQUARIUS project

To strategically reach targeted stakeholder audiences within each social media channel with relevant content, and identify opportunities that can be leveraged to promote AQUARIUS, the AQUARIUS “content territories” have been scoped and defined below in Figure 15. This exercise will guide the content strategy.

Figure 15. AQUARIUS "content territories" informing the scope of and opportunities for AQUARIUS social media communication and dissemination activities.

Hashtag library and mapping key stakeholders in the social media landscape

The most popular hashtags connected to the AQUARIUS content territories have been researched, and a hashtag library has been developed (Appendix 1). The use of relevant hashtags increases content exposure, boosting the opportunity to engage with defined stakeholders and attracting new stakeholders.

Partners LinkedIn and X handles and hashtags

The consortium partners have a well-established presence in the social media networks that will be leveraged (X, LinkedIn) to multiply the project's outreach (Appendix 2).

9.3. Scientific journals and magazines

Scientific peer-reviewed papers produced by AQUARIUS partners or those of the Transnational Access Projects will be a key means of disseminating scientific or technical project results. Relevant magazines (e.g. trade, societal) will be targeted for articles and other content to reach wider audiences.

9.4. Newsletters

The AQUARIUS newsletter will launch in September 2024, i.e. month 7 of the project, to capitalise on the launch of the Research Infrastructure Catalogue, brokerage events and availability of first key Deliverables. The newsletter will be published on a quarterly schedule through the lifecycle of the project. Each issue will convey ongoing project developments, including news on the Transnational Access Funding Calls, training opportunities, a summary of meetings and upcoming events, and will highlight success stories and blogs. It will be distributed via Eudonet, a GDPR-compliant tool and stakeholder management database. Recipients subscribe to the newsletter from the website via a registration form; call-to-action buttons creating awareness for newsletter subscription will be regularly posted on social media and included in communication material, i.e. PowerPoint templates, posters, flyers.

9.5. Blogs and success stories

Blogs are an effective mechanism for storytelling and can foster a spirit of personal connection and engagement with stakeholder audiences thus maximising impact. A minimum of one blog per quarter will be developed and published on the AQUARIUS website. Blogs may take on the format of interviews, personal narratives and traditional articles (targeted towards specific stakeholder groups) and will focus on various themes connected to the project activities, scientific domains, call results and more. Consortium members will be encouraged to share their stories through blogs with editorial support provided by WP7.

Success Stories, comprehensive science blogs, will be developed to demonstrate the importance of enabling transnational access to research infrastructures and to promote the opportunities and achievements of the recipients of the funding grants. The Success Stories will all demonstrate how AQUARIUS activities are addressing societal challenges through its work to integrate, and facilitate access to, research infrastructures.

9.6. Open Science Platforms

Scientific papers arising from AQUARIUS work and that of the AQUARIUS Transnational Access Projects, together with relevant deliverables and outputs will be disseminated via open science platforms, communities and repositories (e.g., Zenodo), including EOSC via Blue-Cloud. The website will host a page describing papers referencing AQUARIUS, with links to where they can be accessed (as they become available). These papers will be promoted on social media and their publications will be communicated in the newsletter.

9.7. Mailing lists and networks

Promotion and communication of the launch of the Research Infrastructure Catalogue, the Transnational Access Funding Calls and dissemination of results will also be activated through mailing lists established in other Transnational Access Projects such as Eurofleets 1,2 and Eurofleets+, JERICO, AssemblePlus and existing programmes, e.g., managed by EMSO ERIC, EMBRC, amongst others.

9.8. Training workshops, conferences & events

Workshops, meetings and events throughout the AQUARIUS project will provide opportunities for communication, knowledge exchange and targeted dissemination activities. Table 4 below provides an overview of the types of meetings and events with an indication of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). As the project progresses, the table will be completed and updated.

Table 4. Workshops, conferences and events organised by AQUARIUS to support communication and dissemination activities

Event type	Description & objectives	TGs targeted	KPI
Brokerage events	To launch the Research Infrastructure Catalogue of the 57 RIs, to raise awareness of planned access to multiple integrated infrastructures and include a series of presentations from each project area followed by networking sessions for researchers.	1, 2, 3, 4, 5	+500 stakeholders at brokerage event
Training workshops	Floating academy/universities, training workshops, summer schools, internship programmes	1,3 and 5	+50 scientists trained
Conferences	Project partners will participate in at least 20 conferences, exhibitions and trade fairs throughout EU and non-EU countries during the project.	1,3,4,5	+20 events
Targeted meetings	Targeted meetings with relevant trade associations to share the results of the project with blue economy SMEs & industry.	3	+5 meetings
Final event	To showcase key, final results and future developments. It will be planned alongside a relevant large-scale European level event or in conjunction with sister projects and recorded for online dissemination to achieve greater impact.	1, 2, 3, 4, 5	+50 participants

AQUARIUS partners will also participate in third-party meetings and events to promote the project and disseminate outputs. A project "Communication and Dissemination Activity Log" has been produced and shared with consortium partners to keep track of the participation of partners to events and meetings, identify the target audience, and type of dissemination activity. Table 5 provides a recent snapshot of the current log, i.e. meetings and events where partners have promoted AQUARIUS in the last few months.

Table 5. AQUARIUS partners Communication and Dissemination Activity Log

Org.	Dissemination activity name*	Date	Type of Activity	Who? Target audience reached	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output	Location (city, country)	Link/Source
MARIS	Presentation of AQUARIUS at Blue-Cloud 2026 General Assembly, during session "Synergies & Exploitation"	5/7/2024	Meetings	Research communities	Introduction of AQUARIUS project and how Blue-Cloud will be supporting its communities to enable their uptake of open science practices in their research	Online	
MI	Presentation at 'Pint of Science' festival	13-15/05/2024	Other	Citizens	Introduction of AQUARIUS and of a number of Marine Institute's research vessels that will be made available via the Transnational Access Calls.	Galway, Ireland	https://pintofscience.ie/event/planet-earth-5
EMSO-ERIC	Presentation at EMRA'24 (Workshop on EU-funded Marine Robotics and Applications)	27-29/05/2024	Conferences	Research communities	Presentation of AQUARIUS in Session 3 "Horizon Projects" of the EMRA'24 workshop to increase visibility to a diverse range of speakers, from ongoing H2020-H-Europe projects, industry, end users and stakeholders.	Arenzano, Italy	https://emra-24.marinerobotics.eu/
VLIZ	Poster at International Underwater Glider Conference (IUGC)	10-14, June 2024	Conferences	Research communities	Poster at International Underwater Glider Conference (IUGC)	Gothenburg, Sweden	https://www.iugc2024.com/
MI	Presentation on AQUARIUS at the 26th European Research Vessel Operators (ERVO) meeting	11-13/06/2024	Conferences	EU institutions	Presentation of AQUARIUS in session 4 "Cooperation, Communications and Outreach"	Vigo, Spain	https://www.ervo-group.eu/
MI	Presentation of AQUARIUS at JERICO-S3 Final General Assembly.	18-21/06/2024	Conferences	Research communities	Presentation of AQUARIUS in a session dedicated to the Key Exploitable Results of JERICO-S3, to promote the Transnational Access Calls and possible synergies after the end of JERICO-S3.	Brest, France	https://www.jerico-ri.eu/events/jerico-s3-final-general-assembly/

9.9. European Commission channels and tools

European Commission and Horizon Europe dissemination channels and tools will be leveraged to further promote AQUARIUS and disseminate outputs. To this end, the following will be explored and used as appropriate:

- EU Research and Innovation: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/projects_en
- Horizon Magazine: <https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/horizon-magazine>
- Horizon Results Booster: <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/> Ends in October/2024: follow-on services will be explored
- Open Research Europe: <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

AQUARIUS has also joined the Mission Ocean Communication Working Group, and participates to monthly meetings. This working group is attended by the communication representatives from various Mission Ocean and Waters funded partners, to discuss upcoming communication opportunities, promote project-related activities and events, and share best practices for the development of outreach material and communication/outreach activities.

10. AQUARIUS Communication and Dissemination: planning and implementation

The earlier sections of this document explain the AQUARIUS approach to communication and dissemination, detailing target stakeholders and objectives, key messages, timing (phases), tools, materials and channels.

This approach is summarised in Table 6, below, together with KPIs for tracking progress.

WP7 leads the design and implementation of the AQUARIUS communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy, with all AQUARIUS partners contributing to dissemination and communication activities (with support from WP7) to ensure the timely promotion of activities and dissemination of outputs. Monthly WP7 meetings are held with partners to coordinate this project-wide activity in order to co-design and share new communication products, highlight upcoming events and opportunities for AQUARIUS, and identify important project activities and outputs for dissemination and communication.

The AQUARIUS SharePoint facility implemented by the project coordinator contains the “communication toolkit” which includes all the branded templates and materials that have been developed to date so that partners can promote the project and disseminate outputs in a consistent style.

Finally, AQUARIUS partner networks and the portfolio of related projects to which they participate represent an important and extensive network of target stakeholders for AQUARIUS and these will be actively used to promote and disseminate AQUARIUS activities and results.

10.1. Communication and dissemination content calendar

A detailed “communication and dissemination content calendar” is developed and maintained by WP7 to plan all communication and dissemination activities and related content. This is guided by project milestones, deliverables, activities and outputs.

Table 7 below contains the “communication and dissemination content calendar” for months 1 to month 18 for this current version of the AQUARIUS Communication and Dissemination Plan (M1-M18).

This calendar is a living document, and reviewed and updated monthly to respond to changing needs and to include ad hoc opportunities that can be leveraged.

In the first six months of AQUARIUS, the communication and, to a lesser extent, dissemination activities have focused largely on Phase 1 “awareness & promotion” (cfr. Section 7.1). While the “promotion” phase continues throughout the project, the “engagement” and “uptake” phases increase in focus from month seven onwards and will be further detailed in the update to this document in month 18.

11. Post-project and AQUARIUS legacy

The AQUARIUS website will remain live for a period of four years after the project completion for the ongoing dissemination of key exploitable results, project information, including the archive of blogs, newsletters, videos, training tutorials and other items.

The legacy of AQUARIUS will be considered in the development of the AQUARIUS legacy video (D7.5) and the Policy Brief (D7.7). Key events and conferences will be identified to disseminate project results in the immediate year following the completion of the project and partners will be identified to disseminate results going forward – to ensure the exploitation of AQUARIUS results and the project legacy.

12. Next steps

This document has outlined the Communication and Dissemination Plan for AQUARIUS. This document will be updated regularly and revised as Deliverable 7.1 and Milestone 34 in Month 18.

Table 6. Overview of AQUARIUS communication and dissemination phases, summarising target groups, objectives, campaigns, types of supporting content, channels and associated KPIs

Phase	TG	Objectives	Campaigns	Content type	Channels	KPIs (project end)
Awareness & Promotion (M1-M48)	TG#1 TG#2 TG#3 TG#4 TG#5	Raise awareness of AQUARIUS, its activities and the societal value of the project.	AQUARIUS kicks-off Get to know AQUARIUS and its people What's coming in AQUARIUS (two TA calls, integrated RI – catalogue) Meet our funded projects	Social media posts Presentations Brochure Factsheet Posters Blog Interviews	Website (news, blogs) Social media Newsletter Events Meetings E-mailing lists	1 toolkit, 2 roll-ups +3000 visits to the AQUARIUS project website +500 followers (Social media) 10 newsletters +2000 brochures distributed +500 downloads infographics & factsheets +500 views for 2 videos +5000 clicks in PPC campaigns
Outreach & Engagement (M7-M48)	TG#1 TG#3 TG#5	To mobilise relevant stakeholder groups to apply to the two TA calls. To trigger applications from Early Career Scientists to the training opportunities. To mobilise relevant stakeholder groups to engage with relevant training webinars or workshops	Register to AQUARIUS brokerage event. Explore our RI catalogue. Transnational Access Calls open– apply now! Learn to use the AQUARIUS TA Calls platform! Join our webinar on FAIR data management!	Social media posts Presentations Posters Flyers/leaflets Training material Factsheets Blog Webinars Interviews First Video	Website (news, blogs) Social media Newsletter Brokerage event Webinars Training events E-mailing lists Events (conferences, workshops, etc)	3000 researchers targeted 500+ citizen science groups contacted 3+ citizen science groups directly engaged in TNA projects 500+ industry stakeholders targeted +50 applications 5+ Mission actions informed about AQUARIUS tools and/or services
Uptake (M7-M48)	TG#1 TG#2 TG#3 TG#4 TG#5	Disseminate key exploitable results from AQUARIUS to the relevant stakeholder groups Disseminate key exploitable results from the funded projects to relevant stakeholder groups	New data flows available – access our AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard. Access our training materials – view/download here. Check out our project results – download/access here Download our AQUARIUS policy brief	Presentations Posters Social media posts Final video Policy brief Blog Webinars	Website (news, blogs) Meetings & events Newsletter Social media Open access scientific publications e.g. Zenodo.org EOSC E-mailing lists Networks e.g. IOC-IODE	70+ participants informed of AQUARIUS vision and recommendations towards marine and freshwater RIs of the future Further KPI will be developed as part of Task 7.3

Table 7. Communication and dissemination content calendar for months 1 to month 18 for this current version of the AQUARIUS Communication and Dissemination Plan (M1-M18)

Phase	Content type	Description	Channel	Status	Date
Awareness	AQUARIUS Branded materials	AQUARIUS branded materials posted to partner institutes to create sense of identity and cohesive branding, including QR codes and website urls to raise visibility of AQUARIUS within partner networks	Mail	Published	
Awareness	Post + Image	Announce AQUARIUS kick-off meeting is taking place online	Social media, website	Published	23/04/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Kick off Meeting wrap-up	Social media	Published	24/04/2024
Awareness	Post + Image + Video	Get to know AQUARIUS - "Pass the Infographic"-video with link to download infographic	Social media	Published	03/05/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	AQUARIUS is featured by the European Atlas of the Seas in their 'Map of the Week' on X, the EMODnet Portal and EC Maritime Forum	Social media, website	Published	03/05/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Get to know AQUARIUS and our people! - A series of five social media posts highlighting AQUARIUS key working areas and WP leads. (1) Facilitating transnational access to a curated catalogue of marine and freshwater research infrastructures	Social media	Published	10/05/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Get to know AQUARIUS and our people! - A series of five social media posts highlighting AQUARIUS key working areas and WP leads. (2) Funding Calls for Transnational Access to European Research Infrastructures	Social media	Published	15/05/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Get to know AQUARIUS and our people! - A series of five social media posts highlighting AQUARIUS key working areas and WP leads. (3) Technical Training	Social media	Published	17/05/2024
Awareness	Powerpoint presentation	AQUARIUS partner (MI) presents at 'Pint of Science' Event in Galway, Ireland	Third party event	Published	15/05/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Promoting AQUARIUS participation at 'Pint of Science' festival	Social media, website	Published	17/05/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Get to know AQUARIUS and our people! - A series of five social media posts highlighting AQUARIUS key working areas and WP leads. (4) Data Management and Open Science Practices	Social media	Published	21/05/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Get to know AQUARIUS and our people! - A series of five social media posts highlighting AQUARIUS key working areas and WP leads. (5) Impact	Social media	Published	23/05/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Get to know AQUARIUS - Opportunities for early career scientists	Social media	Published	28/05/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	AQUARIUS partner (EMSO ERIC) presents at EMRA workshop	Third party event	Published	28-29/05/2024
Awareness	Powerpoint presentation	Promoting AQUARIUS participation at EMRA workshop	Social media, website	Published	29/05/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Leveraging European Maritime Day 2024 social media activity to highlight how AQUARIUS will contribute to the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030 Goals	Social media	Published	03/06/2024

Awareness	Post + Image	Happy World Environment Day from AQUARIUS	Social media	Published	05/06/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Happy World Ocean Day from AQUARIUS	Social media	Published	08/06/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Announcement of AQUARIUS involvement in ERVO meeting	Social media	Published	10/06/2024
Awareness	Poster	AQUARIUS partner (VLIZ) presents poster at International Underwater Glider Conference 2024	Third party event	Published	10-14/06/2024
Awareness	Powerpoint presentation	AQUARIUS partner (MI) presents at 26th annual ERVO meeting	Third party event	Published	11/06/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Promotion of AQUARIUS involvement in International Underwater Glider Conference 2024	Social media	Published	12/06/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Promotion of AQUARIUS involvement in ERVO meeting	Website	Published	13/06/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Leveraging Digital Ocean Forum social media activity to highlight how AQUARIUS will contribute data to the EU DTO	Social media	Published	13/06/2024
Awareness	Infographic	AQUARIUS infographic disseminated at 5th EU Macro-regional Strategies Week	Workshop	Published	12/06/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Promoting AQUARIUS participation to workshop at 5th EU Macro-regional Strategies Week - link to download infographic	Website	Published	13/06/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Getting to know AQUARIUS -Research Infrastructure Categories	Social media	Published	20/06/2024
Awareness	Powerpoint presentation	AQUARIUS partner (MI) presents AQUARIUS at the final JERICO-S3 General Assembly	Third party event	Published	18-21/06/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Promoting AQUARIUS involvement in JERICO-S3 General Assembly	Social media	Published	21/06/2024
Awareness	Presentation	AQUARIUS Partner (MI) represents AQUARIUS at EuroGo-Ship RI Workshop	Third party event	Published	27/06/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Promoting AQUARIUS involvement at EuroGo-Ship RI Workshop	Social media	Published	27/06/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Getting to know AQUARIUS - Meet AQUARIUS partners	Social media	Published	04/07/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Promotion of upcoming AQUARIUS Brokerage Event and link to registration	Website	Published	11/07/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Promotion of upcoming AQUARIUS Brokerage Event and link to registration	Social media	Published	12/07/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Promote subscription to upcoming first Newsletter & link to 'subscribe'	Social media	Published	17/07/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Visit of AQUARIUS Coordinator (MI) to the Newport Catchment Research Facility	Social media	Published	24/07/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Promotion of upcoming AQUARIUS Brokerage Event and link to registration	Social media	Published	26/07/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Countdown to launch of AQUARIUS RI Catalogue at end of August	Social media	Published	01/08/2024
Awareness	Post + Image	Posts to promote AQUARIUS Brokerage Event and "register now" link	Social media, website, email	Pending	Aug-24
Awareness	Post + Image	Promote subscription to upcoming Newsletter & link to 'subscribe'	Social media	Pending	Aug-24
Awareness	Post + Image	Promote launch of new ENVRI website and relevance to AQUARIUS	Social media	Pending	Aug-24
Awareness	Post + Image	Countdown to launch of RI Catalogue - 3 weeks to go	Social media	Pending	Aug-24

Awareness	Post + Image	Highlight delivery of AQUARIUS Call Priorities Report (D3.1) and provide access via download link	Social media, website	Pending	Aug-24
Awareness	Post + Image	Countdown to launch of RI Catalogue - 2 weeks to go	Social media	Pending	Aug-24
Uptake	Post + Image	Highlight delivery of AQUARIUS Data Gaps Report (D6.1) and provide access via download link	Social media, website	Pending	Aug-24
Awareness	Post + Image	Countdown to launch of RI Catalogue - 1 week to go	Social media	Pending	Aug-24
Awareness	Post + Image	Announce upcoming AQUARIUS brokerage events (on site and online) with different regional and thematic focus & links to register	Social media, website	Pending	Aug-24
Engagement	Post + video	Launch of online AQUARIUS RI catalogue	Social media, website, email	Pending	Aug-24
Awareness	Post + Image	Promotion of AQUARIUS website and contents	Social media	Pending	Aug-24
Upcoming: Sept 2024 - July 2025					
Awareness	Blog	Blog #1: Partner blog on work behind RI portfolio	website	Pending	Sep-24
Awareness	Post + Image	Blog #1: Promote partner blog on work behind RI portfolio and links to RI catalogue	Social media, website	Pending	Sep-24
Uptake	Brochure	Highlight delivery of the AQUARIUS brochure and provide access via download link	Social media, website	Pending	Sep-24
Uptake	Poster, brochures	AQUARIUS Partner (AWI) presenting poster at EU Polar Science Week, disseminating brochures	Third party event	Pending	Sep-24
Awareness	Post + Image	Promotion of AQUARIUS involvement at Polar Science Week and relevance to regional scope of AQUARIUS	Social media, website	Pending	Sep-24
Engagement	Post + Image	Announce upcoming AQUARIUS brokerage events highlighting different regional and thematic focus & links to register	Social media, website	Pending	Sep-24
Awareness	Post + Image	Promote Newsletter & link to 'subscribe' ahead of publication of 1st newsletter	Social media	Pending	Sep-24
Awareness	Post + Image	Launch promo campaign for TA Call 1 - announce call definitions and challenges areas (D3.3)	Social media, website	Pending	Sep-24
Engagement	All materials	First AQUARIUS Brokerage Event as side-event at ICES Annual Science Conference 2024	AQUARIUS event	Pending	Sep-24
Awareness	Post + Image	Promotion of AQUARIUS First Brokerage Event - news & key messages, photographs and relevant links to information	Social media, website	Pending	Sep-24
Engagement	Post + Image	Reminder to register for upcoming brokerage events - register now	Social media, website	Pending	Sep-24
Uptake	Newsletter	First quarterly newsletter published	Email campaign	Pending	Sep-24
Awareness	Post + Image	Promotion of first newsletter and encourage subscription	Social media, website	Pending	Sep-24
Uptake	Post + Image	Highlight delivery of AQUARIUS Data Management Plan (D6.2) and provide access via download link	Social media, website	Pending	Sep-24
Engagement	All materials	Second AQUARIUS Brokerage Event as side-event to MonGOOS workshop - MedSea focus	AQUARIUS event	Pending	Oct-24

Uptake	Infographic/ brochure	Disseminate brochures/infographics at EGI 2024 conference (30 Sep - 4 Oct)	Third party event	Pending	Oct-24
Awareness	Post + Image	Promotion of AQUARIUS involvement at EGI 2024 conference	Social media, website	Pending	Oct-24
Awareness	Post + Image	Promotion of second AQUARIUS Brokerage Event - news & key messages, photographs and relevant links to information	Social media, website	Pending	Oct-24
Awareness	Post + Image	4-week countdown to launch of first TA call - direct to all relevant info & encourage registrations to 1st webinar	Social media	Pending	Oct-24
Engagement	Presentations, video, infographic	Training webinar in AQUARIUS data management plans, recorded and shared on website and social media	webinar, website, social media	Pending	Oct-24
Engagement	Post + video	3-week countdown to launch of first TA call - direct to all relevant info & "register now" to 1st webinar	Social media	Pending	Oct-24
Uptake	Brochures	AQUARIUS brochures disseminated at SeaTechWeek	Third party event	Pending	Oct-24
Engagement	Post + Image	2-week countdown to launch of first TA call - direct to all relevant info & "register now" to 1st webinar	Social media	Pending	Oct-24
Engagement	Post + video	1-week countdown to launch of first TA call - direct to all relevant info & "register now" to first webinar	Social media	Pending	Oct-24
Engagement	All materials	Third AQUARIUS Brokerage Event as side-event to MARBLUE conference - Black sea focus (TBC)	AQUARIUS event	Pending	Oct-24
Awareness	Post + Image	Promotion of third AQUARIUS brokerage event - promotion of event, outcomes, photographs and relevant links	Social media, website	Pending	Oct-24
Uptake	Brochures, powerpoint	AQUARIUS partner disseminates brochures/infographics at EOSC 2024 conference (20 - 23 Oct)	Third party event	Pending	Nov-24
Awareness	Post + Image	Promotion of AQUARIUS involvement at EOSC 2024 conference	Social media, website	Pending	Nov-24
Engagement	Presentations, videos, information materials	AQUARIUS brokerage event webinar & FAQ session for first TA call	AQUARIUS webinar	Pending	Nov-24
Awareness	Post + Image	Promotion of AQUARIUS brokerage event webinar, make available recording	Social media, website	Pending	Nov-24
Uptake	Post + Image, reports, videos	Disseminate TA call information and training materials - include download links	Social media, website	Pending	Nov-24
Engagement	Post + Image	Launch First TA call / First TA call is now open "apply now"	Social media, website	Pending	Nov-24
Engagement	Post + Image	AQUARIUS TA Call FAQ webpage is available and promoted	Social media, website	Pending	Nov-24
Engagement	Factsheet, post+ image	AQUARIUS TA Call 1 factsheet is delivered and promoted	Social media, website	Pending	Nov-24
Uptake	Post + Image	Highlight delivery of report of AQUARIUS Brokerage events (D1.2) and provide access via download link	Social media, website	Pending	Nov-24
Awareness	Blog	BLOG#2: Partner blog on the launch of TA calls is published	website	Pending	Nov-24
Awareness	Post + Image	Information on multidisciplinary lighthouse projects as examples for multi RI uses.	website		

Awareness	Post + Image	Promote partner blog#2	Social media, website	Pending	Dec-24
Uptake	Post + Image	Highlight delivery of database with list of all RIs Training requirements for users (D5.1) and provide access via download link	Social media, website	Pending	Nov-24
Engagement	Presentation , video	Training webinar on how to use Access Platform held, and outputs disseminated	webinar, website, social media	Pending	Nov-24
Uptake	Newsletter	Second quarterly newsletter published, includes links to webinar outputs	Email campaign	Pending	Dec-24
Awareness	Post + Image	Promotion of second newsletter and encourage subscription	Social media, website	Pending	Dec-24
Engagement	Post + video	Announce Marine Internship Open Call, call and application form on website - apply now	Social media, website, email	Pending	Dec-24
Awareness	Post + Image	Announcement about AQUARIUS General Assembly to be held in February 2025	Social media, website	Pending	Jan-25
Engagement	Post + Image	Last chance to apply for TA funding; announce closing of TA Call 1	Social media, website	Pending	Jan-25
Engagement	All materials	Targeted meeting with industry representatives	Event	Pending	Jan-25
Engagement	Post + Video	Announce Floating University Open Call, call and application form on website	Social media, website	Pending	Jan-25
Awareness	Post + video	Release teaser of upcoming AQUARIUS promotional video to be released at AQUARIUS general assembly	Social media, website	Pending	Feb/2025
Engagement	Presentations, video, roll-up banners, posters	AQUARIUS General Assembly Meeting	AQUARIUS event	Pending	Feb-25
Awareness	Video	Launch AQUARIUS promotional video to coincide with General Assembly	website	Pending	Mar 2025
Awareness	Post + Image	Promote upcoming operational federated and integrated AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard (ADD) implemented	Social media, website	Pending	Feb-25
Awareness	Post + Image	Highlight delivery of promotional video	Social media, website	Pending	Mar 2025
Uptake	Post + Image	Highlight delivery of AQUARIUS Project Activity Annual Report Year 1 (D1.3) and provide access via download link	Social media, website	Pending	Mar 2025
Awareness	Blog	BLOG#3	website	Pending	Mar 2025
Awareness	Post + Image	Promote blog#3	Social media, website	Pending	Mar 2025
Uptake	Newsletter	Third quarterly newsletter published with download links to AQUARIUS outputs	Email campaign	Pending	Mar 2025
Awareness	Post + Image	Promotion of third newsletter and encourage subscription	Social media, website	Pending	Mar 2025
Uptake	Post + Image	Highlight delivery of Exploitation Plan Outline template (D7.2) and provide access via download link	Social media, website	Pending	May 2025
Awareness	Post + Image	Announce TA projects selected for funding Call 1	Social media, website	Pending	May 2025
Awareness	Factsheet	Highlight delivery of factsheet #2	Social media, website	Pending	May 2026

Engagement	All materials	AQUARIUS booth @ European maritime Day	Third party event	Pending	May 2026
Awareness	Blog	BLOG#4	website	Pending	June 2025
Awareness	Post + Image	Promote blog#4	Social media, website	Pending	June 2025
Uptake	Newsletter	Fourth quarterly newsletter published and encourage subscription	Email campaign	Pending	June 2025
Awareness	Post + Image	Announce TA Projects initiated based on Call 1	Social media, website	Pending	Jun-25
Engagement	Post + Image	4-week countdown begins to launch of second TA call - direct to all relevant info & encourage registrations to informative webinar "apply now"	Social media	Pending	Aug-25
Engagement	Post + Image	3-week countdown begins to launch of second TA call - direct to all relevant info & encourage registrations to informative webinar "apply now"	Social media	Pending	Aug-25
Engagement	Post + Image	2-week countdown begins to launch of second TA call - direct to all relevant info & encourage registrations to informative webinar "apply now"	Social media	Pending	Aug-25
Engagement	Post + Image	1-week countdown begins to launch of second TA call - direct to all relevant info & encourage registrations to informative webinar "apply now"	Social media	Pending	Aug-25
Awareness	Post + Image	Highlight delivery of Selection report from OEP for Call 1 (M18) and Call 2 (M36) (D4.2) and provide access via download link	Social media, website	Pending	Sep-25
Awareness	Post + Image	Highlight launch of Technical Training Hub - Training Material Repository	Social media, website	Pending	Sep-25

13. Appendix 1

Table 8. Hashtag library

Aquatic Ecosystems	Followers	Research & data	Followers	Environment	Followers
#Water	45044	#DATA	6097370	#ClimateChange	165550
#Marine	39992	#Research	631131	#Sustainable	57517
#Biodiversity	34431	#Collaboration	401905	#Conservation	33660
#Nature	24964	#Community	136377	#Chemical	31556
#Ecosystem	6781	#Science	128286	#Protection	21030
#Ocean	5832	#OpenSource	47637	#Plastic	14485
#Ecosystems	2544	#DataManagement	30913	#ClimateCrisis	13876
#Delta	1700	#Connect	29693	#WaterQuality	9616
#Algae	1369	#Knowledge	15311	#NorthSea	7707
#OceanConservation	1227	#Integration	10582	#CarbonNeutral	6909
#habitat	1193	#Volunteer	9463	#NatureBasedSolutions	6284
#Interface	936	#Satellite	7489	#PFAS	5872
#River	623	#Monitoring	6619	#Pollution	5632
#Coastal	579	#OpenData	5920	#PlasticPollution	4349
#Freshwater	474	#Interoperability	5395	#MarineConservation	1634
#Coast	195	#Networks	4823	#Habitat	1198
#Aquatic	160	#Connecting	4714	#Arctic	1079
#CoastalManagement	135	#Cooperation	4594	#NaturalCapital	983
#MarineBiodiversity	105	#MarineBiology	3837	#MarineScience	901
#Basin	76	#EarthObservation	3297	#EcosystemServices	866
#Shoreline	74	#Modelling	2130	#NBS	618
#MarineEcosystems	42	#OpenScience	1951	#Species	323
#Estuary	13	#Oceanography	1178	#Atlantic	323
#CoastalScience	9	#CitizenScience	1029	#Prevent	314
#LandSea	6	#Observation	486	#Danube	290
#CoastalEcology	3	#CoDesign	414	#NatureRestoration	241
#CoastalDevelopment	3	#PublicEngagement	403	#BalticSea	240

Policy	Followers	RIs	Followers	Funding Calls	Followers	Audiences	Followers
#DATA	6097370	#Infrastructure	116538	#Careers	22241681	#Industry	17871
#Strategy	5026845	#Aircraft	47136	#Internship	482497	#PostDoc	16517
#DigitalTwin	13641	#DataCenter	28584	#Opportunity	295173	#Academia	13473
#EU	12072	#Drones	16431	#Internship	122491	#Researchers	9884
#OneHealth	8824	#Facilities	16085	#Apply	73623	#SME	7106
#EUGreenDeal	6842	#Vessel	15483	#ApplyNow	69529	#Scientists	4650
#HorizonEU	3288	#Drone	14002	#Funding	61161	#PhDStudents	1348
#BlueEconomy	3145	#DataCentre	5921	#CareerGrowth	23467	#EarlyCareer	1347
#EUFunding	490	#Catalogue	767	#Grants	3979	#CitizenScience	1054
#SciencePolicy	396	#RV	537	#FundingOpportunities	867	#Policymakers	837
#EUCommission	322	#Aircrafts	427	#ResearchFunding	766	#Citizens	626
#OceanLiteracy	258	#DataInfrastructure	421	#EUFunding	492	#DecisionMakers	442
#EUProject	170	#Experimental	228	#Calls	228	#CoastalCommunities	93
#REA	152	#Fixed	182	#GetFunded	191	#Fishers	67
#MissionOcean	137	#VirtualLab	65	#TrainingOpportunity	141	#Oceanographers	9
#EUResearch	105	#ResearchVessel	59	#TransnationalAccess	7	#EUCitizens	8
#UNOceanDecade	43	#ResearchInfrastructure	45	#GetFunding	2	#Hydrographers	5
#EUMission	26	#ExperimentalResearch	24	#FloatingUniversity	2	#MarineScientists	2
#DigitalTwinOcean	10	#SatelliteServices	16	#fundingCalls	0		
#LandSeaLot	2	#Supersite	2				
#MappingtheOcean	2	#MarineFacilities	1				
#EUDTO	2	#MobileMarineObservationPlatform	0				
#MissionLighthouse	0	#MarineObservationPlatform	0				

14. Appendix 2

Table 9. Partner LinkedIn and Twitter handles

Partner	LinkedIn handle	X handle
The Marine Institute	Marine Institute	@MarineInst
Finnish Meteorological Institute	Finnish Meteorological Institute	@meteorologit
The Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	CSIC	@CSIC
Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR)	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR)	@HcmrInOcean
Norwegian Institute of Marine Research (IMR)	Institute of Marine Research (IMR), Norway	NA
Greenland Institute of Natural Resources (GINR)	Grønlands Naturinstitut	NA
Seascope Belgium (SSBE)	Seascope Belgium	@SeascopeBelgium
Centre for Materials and Coastal Research GmbH (HEREON)	Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon	@HereonHelmholtz
Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research (AWI)	Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research	@AWI_Media
University of Limerick (UL)	University of Limerick (UL)	@UL
National Research and Development Institute Marina Grigore Antipa (INCDM)	National Institute for Marine Research and Development "Grigore Antipa"	NA
Mariene Informatie Service, (MARIS)	MARIS B.V.	NA
The Finnish Environment Institute (SYKE)	Finnish Environment Institute (Syke) - Suomen ympäristökeskus (Syke)	@SYKEint
National Research Council, Italy (CNR)	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	@CNRsocial_
CzechGlobe	CzechGlobe	@czechglobe_offi
Norwegian Institute for Water Research (NIVA)	Norsk institutt for vannforskning (NIVA)	@NIVAforskning
Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences (RBINS)	Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences	NA
Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ)	VLIZ - Flanders Marine Institute	@VLIZnews
European Marine Biological Resource Centre European Research Infrastructure Consortium (EMBRC-ERIC)	EMBRC - European Marine Biological Resource Centre	@EMBRC_EU
Sorbonne University (SU) EMBRC-FR	EMBRC France	@EmbrcFrance
Algarve Centre of Marine Sciences	Universidade do Algarve	@UAlg
Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research CIIMAR	CIIMAR	@CiimarUp
Mercator Ocean (MOi)	Mercator Ocean International	@MercatorOcean
European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL)	EMBL	@embl
The Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI)	SMHI	@SMHI
The Research Institute for Development, France (IRD)	IRD	NA
University of Liège (ULIEGE)	University of Liège	@UniversiteLiege

Partner	LinkedIn handle	X handle
National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology, Italy (INGV)	Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia	@INGV_press
Hydrographic Institute, Portugal	Instituto Hidrográfico - Marinha Portuguesa	NA
Norve Norwegian Research Centre (NORCE)	NORCE Norwegian Research Centre	@NORCEresearch
Oceanic Platform of the Canary Islands (PLOCAN)	Plataforma Oceánica de Canarias (PLOCAN)	@plocan
The Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System (SOCIB)	NA	@socib_icts
The Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO)	VITO	@VITObelgium
European Research Infrastructure Consortium (EMSO ERIC)	EMSO ERIC	@EMSOeu
The National Research-Development Institute for Marine Geology and Geoecology (GeoEcoMar)	GeoEcoMar	@GeoEcoMar
Havstovan Faroe Marine Research Institute (HAV)	NA	NA
Interact-International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring (INTERACT)	INTERACT	@INTERACT66
INKODE Cooperative Society (INKODE)	INKODE soc. coop.	NA
National Institute of Oceanography and Experimental Geophysics, Italy (OGS)	OGS	@OGS_IT
French Research Institute for the Exploitation of the Sea (IFREMER)	Ifremer	@Ifremer_fr
Marine And Freshwater Research Institute (MFRI)	NA	NA
Technical University of Catalonia	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya	@la_UPC
Stichting Nederlandse Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek Instituten [Foundation for Dutch Scientific Research Institutes] (NWO-I)	NWO-I	@NWOnieuws
Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye (TUBITAK)	TÜBİTAK	@Tubitak
Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU)	SLU - Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences	@_SLU